

EXTRACTION OF REFLECTIVITY FROM MICROWAVE BLACKBODY TARGET WITH FREE-SPACE MEASUREMENTS*

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ABSTRACT

We report on the characterization of blackbody target reflections as part of the recent progress on the development of brightness temperature standards for microwave remote sensing at the National Institute of Standards and Technology. The very low reflections from the blackbody targets used in airborne or satellite remote-sensing systems present challenges on how to extract reflection coefficients from the measurements. A full calibration technique was developed for this study by use of a flat aluminum plate used as a known standard in combination with measurements of the empty anechoic chamber. The theoretical basis and measurement procedures are presented. Calibration results validate the method by showing its independence from measurement hardware and conditions. A comparison between the theoretical prediction of reflection coefficients of a free-standing dielectric slab with well documented physical parameters and the de-embedded reflection coefficients from experiments confirms good calibration accuracy. The specific blackbody target used in this study shows well matched properties with a power reflectivity below -40 dB over the entire measurement band (18 GHz to 26 GHz).

Index Terms— Anechoic chamber, blackbody target, free-space calibration, reflection measurement, uncertainty analysis.

1. INTRODUCTION

Characterization of microwave blackbody targets can benefit various climate-related studies that rely on microwave sounding and imaging data obtained from airborne and spaceborne microwave radiometers. At present, brightness temperatures of blackbody targets are approximated as the physical temperature measured by calibrated thermal sensors. This approach has been helpful in short-term weather forecasting where measurements of relative temperature changes are sufficient. However, long-term assessment of climate drift calls for improvements in the precise calibration of the brightness radiation from blackbody targets.

We are developing microwave brightness temperature standards at the National Institute of Standards and Technol-

ogy. The project involves the full characterization of calibration targets by use of standard radiometers that are traceable to primary noise standards [1]. In addition to the brightness temperature measurements, we are also investigating the reflection of the calibration targets as a complementary study. The importance of the reflection measurement arises from its direct link to the emissivity (based on Kirchhoff's radiation law), a parameter that quantifies how close the target is to an ideal blackbody. Also, theoretical derivation of brightness temperature, calculable from the knowledge of target emissivity and physical temperature, serves as a good check against radiometric measurements.

Unlike conventional measurement techniques to characterize material back-scatter properties, such as coaxial transmission-line [2] and open-ended coaxial probe [3] methods, the free-space approach operates in a contactless mode and provides more versatility. Such measurements are usually performed in an anechoic chamber by use of an antenna in connection with a calibrated vector network analyzer (VNA). The antenna acts as a free-space transmitter and receiver. The radiated power from the antenna reaching objects of fixed size varies as a function of their separation distance. Such variation is particularly significant in the near-field region, where the calibration targets are often located for applications in many airborne or spaceborne instruments. Furthermore, calibration targets are designed to produce negligible reflection in their operation band. The measured quantity associated with the targets' reflection is often near or below the uncertainty of the VNA.

2. BACKGROUND

A de-embedding process is required in order to extract the free-space reflection coefficient of an object under test from the background reflections from other objects. Direct measurements of reflection coefficients are usually at the reference plane where the antenna flange is connected to the coax-to-waveguide adapter. Similar to the two-tier calibration technique in the on-wafer environment [4], a one-port calibration is done at the reference plane prior to the free-space measurements (Fig. 1). Next, a few free-space calibration standards of known reflection coefficients are needed in order to correct the error terms arising from the antenna reflection, free-space

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Fig. 1. One-port waveguide calibration is done at the dashed line. The double arrows indicate the error box of the free-space measurements to be solved.

path loss, mismatch between free space and the object under test (OUT), etc. The problem can be modeled as a two-port network terminated by the OUT (Fig. 2). The measured reflection coefficients can be presented by

$$\Gamma_{\text{meas}} = e_1 + \frac{e_2 \Gamma_o}{1 - e_3 \Gamma_o}, \quad (1)$$

where Γ_{meas} is the reflection coefficient measured by the VNA, $e_{1,2,3}$ are the error terms to be corrected: $e_1 = S_{11}$, $e_2 = S_{12}S_{21}$, and $e_3 = S_{22}$. Γ_o is the reflection coefficient of the OUT. The error term e_2 accounts for the fact that the target intercepts only a fraction of the radiated beam. Even if the target were a perfect reflector, only a fraction of the radiated power would be reflected. Physically, the error term e_1 accounts for reflections that occur even when there is no target present. The principal contribution to e_1 is from the antenna itself and from the mismatch between the antenna and free-space. There are also contributions to e_1 from reflections from the chamber walls. e_1 remains almost unchanged once the measurement hardware is set up.

In principle, three different objects with known reflection coefficients are required to calibrate the error terms, which in turn allows us to solve any unknown reflection (Γ_o) from the measurement (Γ_{meas}) as

$$\Gamma_o = \frac{\Gamma_{\text{meas}} - e_1}{e_2 + e_3(\Gamma_{\text{meas}} - e_1)}. \quad (2)$$

Similar to the one-port waveguide calibration in the guided wave condition, one-port free-space calibration con-

Fig. 2. (a): Error box signal flow graph. (b): Objects offset from the original position are equivalent to adding a transmission line in front of objects.

sists of three known standards: a matched load (unloaded anechoic chamber), a short (a flat metal plate), and an offset short (the same metal plate at an offset position). In practice, we measured the offset short at multiple positions to produce redundancy for data fitting. Measurements on these standards can generate a set of equations as (3), where $\gamma = \alpha + j\beta$ (α : loss factor, β : wave number) represents the complex propagation constant, and $\Delta d^{(i)}$ denotes the i th offset position. For simplicity, we assign the short condition as the zero-offset position in (3). The three error terms ($e_{1,2,3}$) can be solved linearly by first setting no loss ($\alpha = 0$) as an approximation. Next the solved error terms along with $\alpha = 0$ are used as starting values to feed a full nonlinear least-squares fit. In the nonlinear fit, all measurements of the offset short contribute equally with all fitting weights set to 1. Once all error terms are solved, any unknown Γ_o can be computed from measurement (Γ_{meas}).

Equation (2) indicates that the errors in eight variables (real and imaginary parts of e_1 , e_2 , e_3 , and Γ_{meas}) contribute to the uncertainty of the target reflection coefficient (Γ_o). The magnitude of Γ_o is often of more interest than its complex

$$\begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -\exp(-2\gamma\Delta d^{(0)}) & (\Gamma_{\text{meas}}^{\text{chamber}} - \Gamma_{\text{meas}}^{\text{offset}(0)}) \exp(-2\gamma\Delta d^{(0)}) \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ 0 & -\exp(-2\gamma\Delta d^{(n)}) & (\Gamma_{\text{meas}}^{\text{chamber}} - \Gamma_{\text{meas}}^{\text{offset}(n)}) \exp(-2\gamma\Delta d^{(n)}) \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} e_1 \\ e_2 \\ e_3 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \Gamma_{\text{meas}}^{\text{chamber}} \\ \Gamma_{\text{meas}}^{\text{offset}(0)} - \Gamma_{\text{meas}}^{\text{chamber}} \\ \vdots \\ \Gamma_{\text{meas}}^{\text{offset}(n)} - \Gamma_{\text{meas}}^{\text{chamber}} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (3)$$

value. The uncertainty of $|\Gamma_o|$ can be expressed as

$$u_{|\Gamma_o|} = \sqrt{\sum_{m,n=1}^8 \frac{\partial |\Gamma_o|}{\partial x_m} \frac{\partial |\Gamma_o|}{\partial x_n} \rho_{mn} u_{x_m} u_{x_n}}; \quad (4)$$

here $x_{m,n} = \Re$ or \Im ($\mathbf{e}_1, \mathbf{e}_2, \mathbf{e}_3$, or Γ_{meas}), and ρ_{mn} is the correlation coefficient. Type-A and type-B uncertainties associated with each term can be calculated from the least-squares fit and instrument measurement uncertainty, respectively. As for the correlation factors, we compute both scenarios, i.e., fully correlated and fully uncorrelated for the cross terms, and take the larger of the two.

3. MEASUREMENT RESULTS

The experimental setup was previously reported elsewhere [5]. Fig. 3 shows the de-embedded reflection magnitude of a circular blackbody target with a diameter of 330 mm. Measurements with different antennas and in different position ranges were used to validate the calibration method. We measured three different conditions: objects in the range of 225 cm to 235 cm with the pyramidal horn and the conical horn, and objects in the range of 0 cm to 10 cm with the pyramidal horn. The results agree well for most frequencies, except for a couple of frequencies at the high end of the band for measurements in the 0 cm to 10 cm range. Generally, the near-field measurements present a great amount of complexity and difficulty. Although the inclusion of the loss factor helps correct the effects, the error associated with the loss factor shows a higher standard deviation (available from the nonlinear data fitting) at higher frequencies than at lower frequencies. Therefore, the occurrence of the discrepancy at high frequencies in near-field measurements is reasonable. This also suggests that

Fig. 3. Calibrated magnitude of reflection coefficients of the target as a function of frequency by use of different antennas and in different measurement ranges.

a more comprehensive model related to the specific radiation pattern, rather than a simple exponential function, would help improve the calibration, particularly in the near-field range. Furthermore, it is noteworthy that the error bars for the measurements using the conical horn are mostly larger than those from the pyramidal horn. The larger error is mainly due to less signal gain produced by the conical horn, which in turn introduced more noise in the measurement data.

Verification by measuring a mismatched airline is a popular way to validate the calibration in coaxial and waveguide measurements. An equivalent method can be realized by use of a dielectric slab in free-space measurements. We checked the calibration accuracy by de-embedding reflection coefficients from the far-field measurements on a dielectric slab made of 1422 cross-linked polystyrene. Such material has been widely used as a standard reference in metrology of material electromagnetic properties [6]. The polystyrene slab had a thickness of 12.94 mm. Its relative permittivity and loss tangent are 2.55 and 0.0006, respectively. Theoretical calculation was made based on these values and used as a reference for checking the experimental results. Fig. 4 shows very good agreement between experiments and theory.

4. CONCLUSION

We have developed and demonstrated a free-space calibration technique to extract the reflection coefficients of the brightness standard at microwave frequencies. The full calibration using known reflective components is needed to correct all the error terms, which allows us to solve for the unknown reflection from any object. The loss factor, accounting for the radiation pattern variation as a function of the separation distance between the antenna and the OUTs, is critical for the cali-

Fig. 4. De-embedded magnitude of complex reflection coefficients of a polystyrene sheet in comparison with the theoretical values.

bration accuracy. The developed calibration technique was validated by testing different measurement hardware and by checking measurements of a well known polystyrene sample against the theory. The calibration target showed a close-to-blackbody property, with its power reflectivity below -40 dB at all measured frequencies.

5. REFERENCES

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